

DESPLIEGUE Y ADOPCIÓN DE SOLUCIONES BASADAS EN INTELIGENCIA ARTIFICIAL DE AYUDA AL DIAGNÓSTICO PARA RETOS DE ATENCIÓN PRIMARIA EN CATALUNYA

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p><i>(Translation from the original abstract in spanish)</i></p>	<p>The adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) solutions in healthcare has grown exponentially in recent years, particularly in medical image analysis for diagnosis. In this context, the Departament de Salut launched the Salut/IA Programme to promote people-centred AI in Primary Care. This paper describes the methodology used to define, procure, implement and monitor AI solutions through innovative public procurement. The approach, based on the framework developed by AQuAS, assesses healthcare needs, market maturity and adoption feasibility. The methodology enabled the definition of contract scope, award criteria, implementation phases, monitoring mechanisms and payment structures, while generating evidence to support future AI deployments.</p>

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